

COGNITIVE ASPECT OF MEASUREMENT UNITS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

Rakhimova Dilnoza Masharipovna

TTA Urganch filiali, Ingliz tili kafedasi o`qituvchisi

Abstract: *this article is intended to identify the usage of length measurement units in the English and Uzbek languages. It expresses huge importance of studying the units of distance measurement by giving citations from the famous linguists' opinions. Moreover, it includes several examples used in both languages to make the ideas clearer, which can be found in fictional books as well. Comparative and descriptive methods were used in this work. At the end of this article all ideas are considered and conclusion as, the aspect of length measurement in linguistics is very broad topic and should be studied as a crucial part of linguistics in both languages, is stated summarizing key points.*

Keywords: *measurement, length, distance, English, Uzbek, national units.*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7675420>

Introduction. Speaking about measurements at the initial stage of the development of human society, it should be emphasized that we are talking about objects commensurate with the size of the person himself. The fingers and toes were the first counting instruments for humans. The same arms, legs and the dimensions of some other parts of the body (palms, wingspans, finger joints) and their movements - step, arm span - served as examples of the first measures of length, which Depman mentioned in a book called "Measurement and the metric system" [1]. All modern science relies on measurements of the observed properties of specific events or objects. Typically, one measurement produces a number associated with a unit of measure: for example, "number-unit pair —10" meters could be the result of a distance measurement. The number-unit pair resulting from the measurement is called the data; when there is more than one data element, they are called data. The numerical part of the data records unique information, while the unit indicates which phenomenon the information refers to: in the "10 meters" datum, "10" is information, and "meters" tell us how to interpret this information. Measurement data usually has some degree of uncertainty. For example, if a ruler is used to measure distance to the nearest centimeter, then it is not enough to specify "10 meters»; the scientist should record that the distance is 10 meters plus or minus 1 centimeter. Without precise measurements, the uncertainty of which is well known, science would not be able to unravel the web of cause and effect that makes up the physical world. And although science is much more than a mere accumulation of measurements, science could not exist without measurements. In all areas of science, millions of phenomena are measured: the weight of a mouse, the response time of a person, the brightness of a star, the temperature of the wind.

Materials and methods. There are some units of length measurement that are commonly used and recognized, at the same time there are some units referring distance that are utilized

abnormally. Although they were widely used in the past, nowadays some people just knows about their existence: Inch is a unit of linear measure equal to one twelfth of a foot 2.54 centimeters. The name inch is derived from the English name for the thumb joint. Even today, this unit of measurement is used in some cases. For example, the diagonal of a television, computer, laptop, cell phone, smartphone monitor is measured in inches.

The foot is a unit for measuring length equal to 12 inches or 30.48 centimeters (0.3048 meter): shallow water no more than a foot deep. The shortest way of writing the unit "foot" is by the abbreviation "ft" (or "ft.") or by a prime symbol (′), 5 feet = 5 ft. = 5′. It is called a foot, because it was originally based on the length of a foot. Yard is a unit of linear measure equal to 3 feet or 36 inches in the United States Customary System or 0.9144 meter in the International System of Units; abbreviated as yd. Moreover, there is a cloth yard, used to measure cloth, is 37 inches long. Yard was also the standard length for arrows. The mile is a measure of distance equal to 5,280 feet; statue mile: After running out of gas we walked two miles to the filling station. Point (0.3528mm) - a point approximately equal to the width of the point that we put on the letter. Barleycorn is thought to be equal to a grain of barley; The barleycorn is a former English unit of length equal to 1/3 of an inch. It is still used as the basis of shoe sizes in English-speaking countries. Line (2.1mm) - a line (6 points) that is close to the traditional 2 millimeters A finger (sometimes fingerbreadth or finger's breadth) is any of several units of measurement that are approximately the width of an adult human finger, including: The digit, also known as digitus or digitus transversus (Latin), dactyl (Greek) or dactylus, or finger's breadth — 3/4 of an inch or 1/16 of a foot. A nail, as a unit of cloth measurement, is generally a sixteenth of a yard or 2 1/4 inches or 5.715 centimeters. The nail was apparently named after the practice of hammering brass nails into the counter at shops where cloth was sold.

Results. Acre is a unit of land measurement in the British Imperial and United States Customary systems, equal to 43,560 square feet, or 4,840 square yards. One acre is equivalent to 0.4047 hectare (4,047 square metres). Derived from Middle English aker (from Old English aecer) and akin to Latin ager (—field), the acre had one origin in the typical area that could be plowed in one day with a yoke of oxen pulling a wooden plow. Furlong is a measure of distance equal to one eighth of a mile; 220 yards or 201.168 meters. The history of the furlong goes back to the Old English furlang < furh (furrow) + lang (long). It is an old English unit of length, based on the length of an average plowed furrow (hence —furrow-long, or furlong) in the English open- or common-field system.

In medicine and related disciplines (anatomy, radiology, etc.) the fingerbreadth (literally the width of a finger) is an informal but widely used unit of measure. In the measurement of distilled spirits, a finger of whiskey refers to the amount of whiskey that would fill a glass to the level of one finger wrapped around the glass at the bottom. Another definition (from Noah Webster): "nearly an inch. Finger is also the name of a longer unit of length used in cloth measurement, specifically, one eighth of a yard or 4 1/2 inches. It is known that the words depicting units of measurement have existed since ancient times and were used in times when units of measurement were not introduced based on the needs of the people. For example, words such as chaqirim, yig'och, manzil, mil, en, qari, qarich, quloch were used with the

compounds such as ko'z yetar yer, ko'z ko'rar yer to describe length in Uzbek language. According to the historical sources it is known that, in ancient times, people used the human body as a unit of measurement. There are even reports that human hair has been used as a unit of length. For example:

Ahmoqni ahmoq desa bir qarich o'sadi; Ikki dunyo bir qadam.

The words qarich and qadam in these proverbs have long been used as a unit of length. Qarich is used to represent the distance between the fingers of the person (the distance between the thumb and the fifth, the smallest finger) and qadam was used to represent the distance between the steps of the person. According to the historical sources it is known that, in ancient times, people used qadam for land surveying and canal digging. These words are still used today in the vernacular. Better understanding of the measurement units is very crucial. Because this topic is widely connected with not only astronomy, mathematics or building, but also it has deep connections with history, linguistics and literature. It must be emphasized that we need to give students an idea of units of measurement in the past. This is especially important in literature classes. Because students may not understand the meaning of measurement units as above examples given in their textbooks.

Conclusion. In this article various units of length measurement in the English and Uzbek languages are analyzed. It was clear that we can see them not only in the mathematical books with concrete numbers but also, they can be found in literature books and folklores. Moreover, several examples of distance measurement units were investigated, in which some measuring words may obtain more than one meanings. The aspect of length measurement in linguistics is very broad topic and can be hardly examined with the help of one article. Therefore, more research in this field is needed.

REFERENCES

1. Depman I.Ya. (1953). Mera i metrisheskaya sistema. Detskaya literature.
2. Zemskova I.P. (1999). Logicheskiy analiz yazikov: Yaziki dinamicheskogo mira. Dubna: Mejdunarodniy universitet prirodi.
3. Clarence L. Barnhart & Robert K. Barnhart. (1998). The World Book Dictionary, Volume one A – K, page 1066.
4. The new Oxford American Dictionary is based on the New Oxford Dictionary of English. (1998). United Kingdom, page 858
5. Simple English Wikipedia, [https://simple.wikipedia.org/wiki/Foot_\(unit\)](https://simple.wikipedia.org/wiki/Foot_(unit))
6. Clarence L. Barnhart & Robert K. Barnhart. (1998). The World Book Dictionary, Volume two L – Z, page 2418.
7. Qodir To'rayev. (2013). Sharq manbalarida o'lchov birliklari.
8. O'zbek tilining izohli lug'ati. Birinchi jild. A – D, Tuzatilgan 2-nashri, 103.